

EFFECT OF CIRCUIT TRAINING ON EXPLOSIVE POWER AMONG FOOTBALL PLAYERS

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of circuit training on explosive power among football players. In this study, 30 students from A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam College, Poondi, Thanjavur were selected as the subjects for this study. They were divided into two groups of fifteen each and assigned as control and experimental group. Experimental treatment was applied only to the experimental group for a period of six weeks. The control group was not given experimental treatment. The circuit training was given thrice a week. After six weeks the final performance of both the control and experimental groups were taken. The significant differences between the means of experimental group and control group for the pre-test and post-test scores were determined by ANCOVA. The level of significance was fixed at 0.05 level of confidence for the degree of freedom 1 and 14. It was observed that the experimental group showed significant improvement on explosive power.

Key Words: Circuit Training, Explosive Power

Introduction:

Circuit training is a practical method entailing some preliminary planning, but beyond that, it needs co-ordination. Athletes find it motivating since it makes conditioning fun and challenging through competition against team mates. Circuit training is a continuous series of exercises attempting to improve as many components of physical fitness as possible especially endurance. Generally, six to twelve stations are up. Selection and sequence of the activities within a lap of circuit is made with consideration given to the continuous nature of the performance. Circuit training workouts may target the entire body or just one specific area, such as the arms, legs, or chest. In addition, circuit training workouts may focus on strength training, aerobics, or a combination of the two; the possibilities are virtually limitless. In general, there are four types of circuit training workouts, and these include a timed circuit, a competition circuit, a repetition circuit, and a sport specific/running circuit (Frietas et al. 2015).

Methodology:

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of circuit training on explosive power among football players. In this study, 30 students from A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam College, Poondi, Thanjavur were selected as the subjects for this study. They were divided into two groups of fifteen each and assigned as control and experimental group. Experimental treatment was applied only to the experimental group for a period of six weeks. The control group was not given experimental treatment. The circuit training was given thrice a week. After six weeks the final performance of both the control and experimental groups were taken. The significant differences between the means of experimental group and control group for the pre-test and post-test scores were determined by ANCOVA. The level of significance was fixed at 0.05 level of confidence for the degree of freedom 1 and 14.

Results:

Table 1: Computation of Mean and Analysis of Covariance of Explosive Power of Experimental and Control Groups

	Experimental Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Pre Test Mean	1.20	1.19	BG	0.001	1	0.001	1.015
			WG	0.041	28	0.001	
Post Test Mean	1.36	1.20	BG	0.184	1	0.184	133.072*
			WG	0.039	28	0.001	
Adjusted Post Mean	1.36	1.20	BG	0.184	1	0.184	133.952*
			WG	0.037	27	0.001	

* Significant at 0.05 level, Table value for df 1 and 28 was 4.20, 1 and 27 was 4.21

The above table indicates the adjusted mean value of explosive power of experimental and control groups were 1.36 and 1.20 respectively. The obtained F-ratio of 133.95 for adjusted mean was greater than the table value 4.21 for the degrees of freedom 1 and 27 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence. The result of the study indicates that there was a significant difference among experimental and control groups on explosive power. The above table also indicates that both pre and post test means of experimental and control

groups differ significantly. The pre, post and adjusted post mean values of explosive power of both experimental and control groups are graphically represented in the figure-I.

Figure 1: Shows the Mean Values on Explosive Power of Experimental Group and Control Groups

Conclusion:

It was observed that the experimental group showed significant improvement on explosive power.

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